

WATER ENTRY OF ASYMMETRIC WEDGES THROUGH PARTICLE IMAGE VELOCIMETRY

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we utilize particle image velocimetry (PIV) to experimentally investigate the asymmetric water impact of a rigid wedge. Different wedge heel angles are studied to understand the role of a geometric asymmetry on the flow physics and pressure field. Experiments are performed on a rigid wedge with 37° deadrise angle impacting the water in free fall at different heel angles. The pressure field in the fluid is obtained by integrating Poisson equation, in which PIV data are used to compute the forcing term as well as the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions. Results demonstrate that the impact configuration modulates the hydrodynamic loading and the flow physics. Specifically, the velocity field is maximized in the vicinity of the keel for large heel angles rather than in the pile-up region, as for the case of small heel angles. However, as the entry depth increases, the location where the velocity is maximized moves from the keel to the pile-up and, at the same time, flow separation initiates at the keel. The reconstructed pressure field is also influenced by the heel angle, whereby we observe variations in both the magnitude and distribution of the pressure field.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hull slamming is a complex fluid-structure interaction that takes place when a blunt body penetrates the water surface [1-2]. During such an event, the impacting body must sustain a severe hydrodynamic loading in a very short time duration. This impulsive loading may induce considerable vibration and, sometimes, structural failure. As the use of lightweight composite materials in marine structures grows, it becomes critical to accurately predict hull slamming and understand its dependence on salient physical and geometrical parameters of the impacting structure.

A rigid wedge is often utilized as prototype geometry for the analysis of hull slamming problems [2]. The hydrodynamic loading, pile-up evolution, and flow separation in the vicinity of the wedge may significantly be influenced by asymmetries during the impact. However, most of the available experimental studies are limited to symmetric impacts, in which a symmetric wedge vertically impacts the water surface [3-4]. The effect of the heel angle on the impact dynamics of a wedge entering the water surface has been studied in [5] and [6]. Beyond these experimental efforts, theoretical solutions and computational schemes have been recently proposed for the analysis of asymmetric water entry [7-12].

Here, we leverage the experimental technique based on particle image velocimetry (PIV) proposed by Panciroli and Porfiri [13] and Nila et al. [14] to analyze asymmetric water impact. PIV is used in [13, 14] to measure the flow kinematics and kinetics during the symmetric impact of a rigid wedge. We consider a symmetric wedge with 37° deadrise angle vertically entering a quiescent water surface from a falling height of 50 cm. We parametrically vary the heel angle and PIV measurements are conducted to obtain the fluid velocity during the impact. Poisson equation is integrated in the fluid to reconstruct the pressure field from PIV measurements. An expanded version of this work can be found in [15].

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Drop-tower and wedge apparatus

We use the experimental setup described in [13]. Briefly, the experimental setup consists of a transparent tank with dimensions of $800 \times 320 \times 350 \text{ mm}^3$ which is fixed on an aluminum frame. Two 1.5 m long aluminum rails are utilized to control the vertical movement of the wedge until the onset of the impact, see Fig 1. The wedge runs along the rails using a sledge that is rigidly connected to the wedge. The deadrise angle of the wedge is 37° [6] and has a rectangular base with dimension $190 \times 200 \text{ mm}^2$. The frame of the wedge is fabricated from ABS material and printed with a rapid prototyping machine. We glue an external layer of 3.175 mm thick balsa wood to the frame through an epoxy adhesive.

Figure 1: Experimental apparatus and components of the data acquisition. The wedge view and rail positions are illustrated in the inset.

2.2 Data acquisition system

We use a time-resolved planar PIV system to analyze the asymmetric water impact. Specifically, two high speed Phantom cameras V.9.1 and a 5 W Nd:YAG Ray Power laser source are utilized in the data acquisition system, see Fig. 1. The cameras synchronously capture two adjacent regions of the fluid bulk with the acquisition rate of 4 kHz. A target with the reference grid size of $8 \times 8 \text{ mm}^2$ is utilized to calibrate and merge the recorded images at each frame for PIV analysis. The overall image dimensions are $400 \times 160 \text{ mm}^2$. Silver-coated hollow glass spheres with a mean diameter of $44 \mu\text{m}$ are used as tracer particles. The particles are illuminated through the laser source at the mid-span of the wedge where three-dimensional effects are negligible [16]. The cameras capture 100 images during the impact which corresponds to 25 ms.

2.3 Experimental conditions

The heel angle is adjusted by rotating the wedge counterclockwise with increments of 5° , from $\theta=0^\circ$ (symmetric case) to 35° , with respect to the sledge. The right and left deadrise angles of the wedge at the onset of the impact, $t=0$, are $\beta_1=\beta+\theta$ and $\beta_2=\beta-\theta$, respectively, see Fig. 2. During the impact, the wedge may rotate of an angle α . The same impact height of 50 cm is considered for all the tests. We conduct three repetitions for each experiment for a total number of 24 drop tests. All the experiments are conducted under laboratory illumination.

Figure 2: (a) The wedge configuration at the onset of the impact. (b) Example of the wedge position during the impact.

3 DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 PIV analysis

A fast Fourier transform cross-correlation algorithm and a multi-grid scheme with a 50% interrogation window overlap are used to analyze PIV images through the open source Matlab code “PIVlab” [17]. We utilize a decreasing interrogation window size of 64×64 , 32×32 , 16×16 pixels.

To identify the wedge boundaries and the free surface, an image masking process is placed manually in a Matlab script at each frame. The velocity field estimated from PIV data are smoothed through a spline smoothing technique.

3.2 Pressure reconstruction

The fluid is assumed to be ideal and incompressible, thus the fluid is described as

$$\frac{\partial p(x, y, t)}{\partial x} = -\rho \left(\frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial t} + u(x, y, t) \frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial x} + v(x, y, t) \frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \right) \quad (2a)$$

$$\frac{\partial p(x, y, t)}{\partial y} = -\rho \left(\frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial t} + u(x, y, t) \frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial x} + v(x, y, t) \frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \right) \quad (2b)$$

$$\frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (2c)$$

where $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the fluid density, u and v are velocities along the x and y directions, respectively, and p is the pressure. We derive Poisson equation by differentiating Eqs. (2a) and (2b) with respect to the x and y , respectively, summing them, and utilizing Eq. (2c). Thus, we find [18]

$$\frac{\partial^2 p(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p(x, y, t)}{\partial y^2} = -\rho \left(\left(\frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \frac{\partial u(x, y, t)}{\partial y} + \left(\frac{\partial v(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

To obtain the pressure field in the fluid bulk, a Dirichlet boundary condition is imposed on the free surface (S_{SL} and S_{SR} , see Fig. 3) and the boundary of the acquired image (S_{BL} , S_{BR} , and S_{BB}). A Neumann boundary condition is applied on the fluid-wedge interface (S_{IL} and S_{IR} , see Fig. 3). We use known velocity field obtained from PIV analysis to satisfy both Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions. In particular, we prescribe the fluid pressure and the normal gradient of the pressure on the wedge surface $\partial p / \partial n$ to satisfy the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions, respectively.

We implement a time marching scheme to solve Eq. (3). We select a Cartesian uniformly spaced grid consistent with the dimension of the PIV data matrix. We introduce ghost points outside the fluid domain close to the wedge boundary to apply the Neumann boundary conditions, see Fig. 3. The grid points are comprised of points inside the fluid domain Ω , on the boundaries $\partial\Omega$, and the ghost points close the boundary $\partial\Omega$, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the computational domain, where a five point centered differences stencil utilized for the discretization of the Poisson equation (left panel). Illustration of ghost points and fluid points used to impose the Neumann boundary conditions (right panel).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Heel angle effect on the velocity field

Here, we illustrate the influence of the heel angle on the velocity field. Figure 4 demonstrates acquired PIV images overlaid with streamlines and the contour plots of the velocity magnitude for $\theta=0^\circ$ at $t=5$ ms and 15 ms. Results reported in Fig. 4 confirm that the velocity field is maximized in the pile-up for symmetric impact [13].

To elucidate the effect of the heel angle on the fluid flow, we illustrate the velocity field for $\theta=20^\circ$ and 30° in Figs. 5 and 6 at the same time instants. While rather minor differences are seen between Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Figure 6 shows that the velocity field is maximized in the proximity of the keel and, as the wedge penetrates, the maximum velocity location moves from vicinity of the keel to the left pile-up differently compared to velocity fields corresponding to smaller heel angles. Moreover, flow separation is observed at the keel as the entry depth increases. Flow separation continuously grows in the right side of the wedge and does not collapse during the selected time for the impact.

4.2 Pressure field

In Figs. 7 and 8, we display the pressure field for $\theta=0^\circ$ and 20° , respectively, at $t=5$ ms and 15 ms. Results show that the maximum pressure is located in the water pile-up region for $\theta=0^\circ$ and 20° [13]. However, the pressure field is significantly influenced by large the heel angles. As the heel angle increases, the pressure increases in the left pile-up region and decreases in the vicinity of the keel. Further, the pressure field attains negative values along the wetted length of the wedge as the entry depth increases during the impact.

In addition, Fig. 9 illustrates the pressure field at the onset of the flow separation ($t=3.5$ ms) for $\theta=30^\circ$. The pressure field at the onset of the flow separation is negative in the right side of the wedge, which is a footprint of the flow separation [19].

5 Conclusion

PIV has been utilized to measure the flow physics during asymmetric impact and aid in analysis of fluid-structure interaction during water entry. Specifically, experiments have been performed on a rigid wedge with deadrise angle 37° , falling vertically from a height of 50 cm. The pressure has been evaluated by solving the Poisson equation, whose kinematic components have been predicted from PIV data.

Results show that the flow physics is modulated by the heel angle, whereby the maximum velocity is attained in the vicinity of the keel for large heel angles in contrast to impacts with small heel angles. For heel angles of 30° and 35° , as the entry depth increases, the location where the velocity is maximized moves from the keel to the left pile-up and, at the same time, flow separation initiates at the keel. Further, we find that the reconstructed pressure field depends on the heel angle, and we

observe significant asymmetries in the pressure distribution with respect to the keel as the heel angle increases.

Figure 4: Acquired high speed images overlaid with streamlines and contour plots of the velocity magnitude in m/s at $t=5$ ms (a and b) and at $t=15$ ms (c and d) for $\theta=0^\circ$.

Figure 5: Acquired high speed images overlaid with streamlines and contour plots of the velocity magnitude in m/s at $t=5$ ms (a and b) and at $t=15$ ms (c and d) for $\theta=20^\circ$.

Figure 6: Acquired high speed images overlaid with streamlines and contour plots of the velocity magnitude in m/s at $t=5$ ms (a and b) and at $t=15$ ms (c and d) for $\theta=30^\circ$.

Figure 7: Pressure distribution in kPa for a heel angle of 0° at different time instants.

Figure 8: Pressure distribution in kPa for a heel angle of 20° at different time instants.

Figure 9: Pressure distribution in kPa at the onset of the impact for a heel angle of 30° .

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